

VOCABULARY AS A BASIC FOUNDATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: *Through this article, we are going to explore important peculiarities of teaching vocabulary at school, college and lyceums. Moreover, different ways of demonstrating vocabulary for learners were discussed.*

Key words: *curriculum, barrier, enrichment, comprehensible, practical aim, productive, receptive, mental lexicon.*

Teaching vocabulary is a very important objective in the curriculum. According to psychologists, human beings learn the life experiences by words, because thoughts are made by words. Word is a central unit of a language: language first of all is the system of words. Without a sufficient vocabulary, students cannot communicate effectively and express ideas. Having a limited vocabulary is also a barrier that prevents students from learning a foreign language. If learners do not know how to expand their vocabulary, they gradually lose interest in learning. The necessity of vocabulary enrichment is pointed out in curriculum. Fortunately, for students and teachers, the most vocabulary growth takes place through incidental learning, that is, through exposure to comprehensible language in reading, listening, speaking, audios and videos and so on. It is necessary to study both theoretical and practical approaches to teaching vocabulary. Thus, knowing the vocabulary selecting criteria is significant for an effective learning.

The main practical aim of teaching vocabulary in the primary and secondary schools is to develop the learners' vocabulary subskills as a basic component of all language and communicative activities. One should realize that the terms “vocabulary” and “words” are not the same.

Learning a new language is basically a matter of learning the vocabulary of that language. Not being able to find the words you need to express is the most frustrating experience in speaking another language. Without doubt vocabulary is not the only thing you have to know about the language. Other levels of language (grammar, phonetic, phonological, and stylistic) are also important. Nevertheless it is possible to have good knowledge of how the language system works and yet not be able to communicate in it; whereas if we have the vocabulary we need assimilate to communicate.

Anyone who learns a new language is likely to recognize more words than he/she can produce. It is difficult to produce a word correctly. It is necessary to pronounce or spell it in the right way, to use it in the correct grammatical form, to use it appropriately to the context. It may therefore be important for a teacher to decide which words are appropriate and relevant for students age and stage. What words can form the ‘productive’ or ‘active’ vocabulary? The teacher also should decide which words she/he wishes her/his students merely to recognize. In other words, what words are considered as the ‘receptive’ or ‘passive’ vocabulary. The production of words (while speaking or writing) in the target language takes much greater efforts from the learner. Of course, in productive vocabulary, the learner has an advantage to choose the word he wishes to use:

whereas in receptive vocabulary (as in listening or reading) he has to handle with the language level of the speaker or writer.

Vocabulary can be defined, roughly, as the words we have to teach in a foreign language class. However, a new item of the vocabulary may occur not in the form of a single word: for example, pen-holder and merry-go-round, which are made up of two or three words but express a single idea. There are also multi-word idioms such as take the bull by the horns, where the meaning of the phrase cannot be deduced from the analysis of the component words. A useful convention would be to cover all such cases as vocabulary «items» rather than «words». It is also called mental lexicon that is «vocabulary in mind». It consists of the smallest independent meaningful unit of speech. These units of speech are called words. The words have the word forms and meanings assigned to them. Words in the mental lexicon create lexical networks. Once activated, a lexical item stimulates the spreading of other associated lexical items, which in its turn causes the activation of a bigger network. Mental lexicon is stored in our memory and it is the process of mapping the meanings in the mind and putting these memory traces into some word groups.

Mental lexicon performs the functions of word storage, retrieval, comprehension and use. The storage of words in the mental lexicon is the result of a person's cognitive processes in real-world situations. As a result of cognitive processes, the words make up the situation sets. These are fairly obvious characteristics, and one or the other will be perceived by the learner when encountering the item for the first time. In teaching, we need to make sure that both these aspects are accurately presented and learned. Another point is grammar. The grammar of a new item will need to be taught if this

is not obviously covered by general grammatical rules. An item may have an unpredictable change of form in certain grammatical contexts or may have some idiosyncratic ways of connecting with other words in sentences; it is important to provide learners with this information at the same time as we teach the basic form. When teaching a new verb, for example, we might give also its past form, if this is irregular (go, went), and we might note if it is transitive or intransitive. Similarly, when teaching a noun, we may teach to present its plural form, if irregular (Toot, feet), or draw learners' attention to the fact that it has no plural at all (advice, information). We may present verbs such as want and enjoy together with the verb form that follows them (want+to do, enjoy+going), or adjectives or verbs together with their following prepositions (wait for, listen to). The collocations typical of particular items are another factor that makes a particular combination sound «right» or «wrong» in a given context. So this is another piece of information about a new item which it may be worth teaching.

To sum up all information above it should be noted that vocabulary knowledge is not something that can ever be fully mastered; it is something that expands and deepens over the course of a lifetime. Instruction in vocabulary involves far more than looking up words in a dictionary and using the words in a sentence. Vocabulary is acquired incidentally through indirect exposure to words and intentionally through explicit instruction in specific words and word-learning strategies.

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